

MAGCCINE

MAGNETIC COOLING FOR VACCINES

Data Management Plan

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Version 1

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MAGCCINE

PROJECT IDENTIFICATION

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Project duration:	48 months
Project Officer	Darina Botsova
Project Coordinator	João Horta Belo
Consortium Partners	Universidade do Porto (U.PORTO) Universidade de Aveiro (U.AVEIRO) Universidad de Sevilla (U.SEVILLA) Univerza v ljubljani (U.LJUBLJANI) Helium 3 Technologies and Consulting sl (HELIUM3) Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) Universite Grenoble Alpes (UGA) MagREESource (MagREESource)

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Table of Contents

1.	PROJECT SUMMARY	5
2.	DATA SUMMARY	6
2.1.	RE-USE EXISTING DATA	6
2.2.	TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA GENERATED	6
2.3.	PURPOSE OF THE DATA GENERATED	7
2.4.	EXPECTED SIZE OF THE DATA	8
2.5.	ORIGIN/PROVENANCE OF THE DATA	9
2.5.1.	GENERATED DATA.....	9
2.5.2.	RE-USED DATA.....	9
2.6.	DATA UTILITY - OUTSIDE PROJECT	9
3.	FAIR DATA PRINCIPLES.....	10
3.1.	MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA.....	10
3.2.	MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE	10
3.2.1.	REPOSITORY	10
3.2.2.	DATA	10
3.2.3.	METADATA	10
3.3.	MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE	11
3.4.	INCREASE DATA RE-USE	11
4.	OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS.....	12
5.	ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES.....	13
6.	DATA SECURITY	14
7.	ETHICS.....	15
8.	HISTORY OF CHANGES.....	16

1. PROJECT SUMMARY

Every year 1.5 million lives are lost worldwide due to insufficient access to vaccination while, paradoxically, over 50% of all produced vaccines are wasted, mostly due to ineffective temperature control during storage/transportation. The major challenges of the vaccine cold chain are the evermore strict limitations imposed on their aerial transport due to the safety hazards of refrigerant gases, the high-power demand of active refrigeration devices in last-mile deliveries where the electricity supply is unreliable, and the significant carbon footprint of high global warming potential (GWP) refrigerants. The Magccine project aims to revolutionise the vaccine cold chain by developing a clean and efficient solid-state magnetic refrigerator based on a novel approach: the rotating magnetocaloric effect (RMCE) – a recent (2023) patent-pending technology by project partners (PCT/IB2024/055783 in 13/06/2024). By reducing the amount of permanent magnets required, the RMCE is expected to enable drastic cuts in the device's production cost, volume and weight while enhancing efficiency without the use of any high GWP or hazardous refrigerant gases, highlighting its role as a key enabling technology for tackling vaccine cold chain challenges. Magccine aims to develop and optimise a fully operational prototype for vaccine refrigeration in the 2-8 °C temperature range required by most vaccines, addressing the Generation of clean cooling and clean cold chain transportation categories of this Challenge. To this end, this project requires top-level expertise in magnetocaloric materials, magnetic field design, thermodynamic simulations and heat pumps, which are perfectly matched by the complementary expertise of the five academic institutions (U.Porto, CNRS, U. Seville, U.Aveiro, U.Ljubljana) and the two industrial partners (MagRESource, Helium 3). Our endeavours will be guided by an experienced global board that includes key global leaders such as WHO, UNICEF, Cemafruid, APIRAC, IIR, Medgree, and Addvolt.

2. DATA SUMMARY

The MAGCCINE project will generate and re-use a diverse range of data to support the development of an innovative RMCE-based refrigeration system for vaccine cold chain applications. This includes experimental data on magnetocaloric materials, thermodynamic and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, and prototype performance measurements. Additionally, existing datasets on material properties, thermodynamic models, and vaccine cold chain logistics will be leveraged to optimise system efficiency. Special emphasis will be placed on developing and refining Active Magnetic Regenerator (AMR) designs to enhance heat transfer and cooling performance. The generated data, estimated to range between 0.6 - 1 TB, will originate from laboratory experiments, numerical simulations, and industry reports. This information will be invaluable to researchers in materials science, refrigeration technology, and sustainable energy, as well as to industries involved in cold chain logistics, policymakers promoting clean cooling solutions, and global health organisations aiming to improve vaccine storage efficiency.

2.1. RE-USE EXISTING DATA

The MAGCCINE project will re-use existing data related to magnetocaloric materials, thermodynamic modeling, and vaccine cold chain logistics. Specifically:

- **Magnetocaloric materials:** Existing experimental datasets on magnetocaloric alloys' thermal and magnetic properties from all MAGCCINE consortium partners, especially from U.Aveiro and U.Porto.
- **Thermodynamic models:** Pre-existing simulation models for heat transfer and refrigeration cycles.
- **Cold chain performance data:** Reports from WHO, UNICEF, and other relevant sources detailing vaccine loss rates and energy consumption patterns.
- **Active Magnetic Regenerator (AMR) designs:** Data from previous studies on the impact of different regenerator geometries and flow dynamics (data from ULjubljana).

Some proprietary or outdated datasets were considered but discarded due to data obsolescence, restricted access, or misalignment with MAGCCINE's specific technological approach.

2.2. TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA GENERATED

The MAGCCINE project will generate various types of data, including experimental, simulation, and technical documentation, in multiple standardized formats to ensure usability and interoperability. MAGCCINE will generate and re-use data in the following formats:

- **Experimental data:** Temperature variations, entropy changes, thermal response of magnetocaloric materials (CSV, JSON, Excel). Magnetic response data, Hot disk and Laser flash excitation, scanning electron microscopy-SEM pictures, energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy-EDS or atomic force microscopy-AFM data or even X-ray diffraction-XRD patterns are other types of data that will be created (ASC, DAT, RAW, RAS, JPEG and PNG).
- **Simulation data:**
 - Thermodynamic modeling of RMCE-based refrigeration cycles (MATLAB, COMSOL, Python-compatible formats, STL geometry files).
 - Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations of heat exchange within the AMR (using computational tools such as COMSOL, ANSYS, OpenFOAM).
 - Finite Element Analysis (FEA) of the AMR (ABAQUS) mechanical stresses.
 - Finite element method-based software such as FFlux (Altair).
- **Prototype performance data:** Cooling efficiency, energy consumption, mechanical stress tests, Life cycle assessment and assembly (field and regenerator) (log files, spreadsheets, databases, ISO referentials).
- **Technical reports and documentation:** System design, experimental protocols, minutes, reports, deliverables, abstracts, presentations and performance metrics (PDF, DOCX, PPTX, XLSX, LaTeX).

2.3. PURPOSE OF THE DATA GENERATED

The data generated in the MAGCCINE project serves multiple purposes that are aligned with its overarching goal of developing an innovative magnetocaloric refrigeration system for vaccine storage.

The primary objectives of data generation include:

- **Advancing Scientific Knowledge** – The project will generate experimental and simulation data on magnetocaloric materials, thermodynamic properties, and system performance, contributing to fundamental research in solid-state cooling.
- **Optimizing System Design** – By analysing the thermal, magnetic, and mechanical behavior of materials and components, the data will be used to refine the design of the Rotating Magnetocaloric Effect (RMCE)-based refrigeration system, improving its efficiency, reliability, low weight and cost-effectiveness.
- **Validating experimental and computational Models and Prototypes** – Thermodynamic models and prototype performance tests will ensure the accuracy of simulations, enabling

data-driven design improvements and reducing development risks (ensure accuracy in predicting magnetocaloric cooling performance).

- **Building confidence in the obtained data**, thereby increasing its robustness and reproducibility.
- **Supporting Industrial and Market Adoption** – Performance metrics, lifecycle assessments, and cost-benefit analyses will provide key insights for potential industrial adoption, ensuring that the technology meets commercial viability and regulatory requirements.
- **Facilitating Dissemination and Exploitation** – Data will support the creation of scientific publications, patents, policy briefs, and market reports, ensuring that MAGCCINE’s results broadly impact academia, industry, and policymakers.
- **Enabling Reproducibility and Future Research** – By adhering to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles, the project ensures that datasets remain accessible to researchers and industry stakeholders for future advancements in sustainable refrigeration. Building confidence in the obtained data, thereby increasing its robustness and reproducibility.
- **Allowing the comparison and refinement** of measurement techniques, particularly for RMCE;

2.4. EXPECTED SIZE OF THE DATA

The MAGCCINE project is expected to generate and manage a total estimated data volume of 0.6 – 1 TB, depending on the number of experimental iterations and refinements in computational models.

The key data categories and their respective estimated sizes include:

- **Experimental Materials Data (~100 GB over the project’s duration):** Data collected from laboratory tests on magnetocaloric materials, including measurements of temperature variations, entropy changes, and thermal response.
- **Thermodynamic Simulation Data (~500 GB):** Computational models and simulations of the Rotating Magnetocaloric Effect (RMCE), heat transfer analysis, and system performance predictions. These datasets will be generated using MATLAB, COMSOL, and Python-based tools.
- **Prototype Performance Logs (~50 GB for prototype):** Data from real-world-like conditions testing of the MAGCCINE refrigeration prototype, including cooling efficiency, energy consumption, mechanical stress tests, and long-term stability assessments.

- **Technical Reports & Documentation (~10-20 GB):** Comprehensive project documentation, including design blueprints, experimental protocols, system architecture descriptions, and performance assessments in formats such as PDF, DOCX, and LaTeX.
- **Total estimated volume:** 0.6 - 1 TB, depending on experimental iterations and model refinements.

This data volume is manageable within the project's allocated storage resources. To ensure long-term accessibility, key datasets will be stored in institutional servers and open-access repositories. The estimated data size may evolve based on experimental progress and additional validation requirements.

2.5. ORIGIN/PROVENANCE OF THE DATA

The data in the MAGCCINE project originates from a combination of:

2.5.1. GENERATED DATA

- New experimental results from laboratory testing and characterisation of magnetocaloric materials.
- Simulation outputs from thermodynamic modeling of the RMCE system.
- Performance data from prototype refrigeration testing.

2.5.2. RE-USED DATA

- Magnetocaloric materials databases (from prior research and scientific publications).
- Thermodynamic and refrigeration efficiency models (published in past studies).
- Cold chain logistics reports (from WHO, UNICEF, and industry partners).

2.6. DATA UTILITY - OUTSIDE PROJECT

MAGCCINE's data could benefit a broad range of stakeholders, including:

- **Scientific community:** Researchers in magnetocaloric refrigeration, thermodynamics, and materials science.
- **Industry and manufacturers:** Companies in HVAC, cold chain logistics, and sustainable refrigeration.
- **Healthcare and NGOs:** WHO, UNICEF, and Gavi for improving vaccine distribution in remote regions.
- **Policy and regulatory bodies:** EU institutions and environmental agencies focus on sustainable refrigeration technologies and emissions reduction.

3. FAIR DATA PRINCIPLES

The MAGCCINE project follows FAIR Data Principles to ensure data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

3.1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

To ensure data findability, all datasets in the MAGCCINE project will be/have:

- **Indexed with clear metadata**, including descriptions, formats, and keywords.
- A **Digital Object Identifier (DOI)** will be assigned to publicly available datasets.
- Metadata will comply with **Dublin Core and DataCite standards**.
- **Persistent identifiers** (DOIs or similar) will be used to ensure long-term discoverability and citation.
- **Search keywords** will be included in metadata to enhance discoverability.
- Metadata will be structured to allow **search engines and data repositories to harvest and index the data**.

3.2. MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

The MAGCCINE project aims to make its data as openly accessible as possible while respecting confidentiality and intellectual property constraints.

3.2.1. REPOSITORY

- Open-access data will be published in **Zenodo and institutional repositories**.
- Arrangements will be made to ensure long-term access and identifier resolution.

3.2.2. DATA

- Some proprietary datasets may be restricted due to confidentiality agreements.
- Embargo periods may be applied for intellectual property protection as described in the Grant and Consortium Agreement (e.g., patent applications).
- Access to restricted data will be granted case-by-case under controlled conditions.

3.2.3. METADATA

- Metadata will be openly available under CC0 (public domain dedication).
- Metadata will contain information to enable the user to access data.
- Documentation will be provided to facilitate data usability.

3.3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Ensuring data is interoperable, MAGCCINE will facilitate collaboration with other research projects, industrial applications, and potential users, allowing its findings to be widely accessible and usable in various contexts.

- Standardised formats (**CSV, JSON, MATLAB, COMSOL**) will be used.
- **Dublin Core** and **FAIR metadata principles** will be followed.
- Generated ontologies or vocabularies will be openly published.
- Qualified references will link project data to relevant external datasets.

3.4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE

Focusing on increasing data re-use, MAGCCINE will aim to maximise the data's value beyond the project's life, allowing it to be integrated into a wide array of future research and applications. This enhances the project's impact and contributes to the broader scientific and technological communities.

- Documentation will include **methodology, variable definitions, and units of measurement**.
- Where applicable, data will be **licensed under Creative Commons (CC-BY) or Open Data Commons**.
- Data provenance will be **thoroughly documented**.
- Quality control measures will ensure **data accuracy and integrity**.

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4. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

In addition to data, the MAGCCINE project will generate other research outputs such as software tools, thermodynamic models, experimental protocols, system designs, and technical reports.

- Software and simulation models **will be deposited in open repositories.**
- Technical prototypes **will be shared with relevant stakeholders.**
- **Open-source tools developed in the project will follow FAIR software principles.**

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

The MAGCCINE project allocates data storage, management, and long-term preservation resources through institutional servers and trusted repositories like Zenodo and OpenAIRE. Data management costs are covered within the project's budget, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles.

- **Storage:** Data will be stored using project-partner institutional servers and cloud-based repositories (e.g., Zenodo, OpenAIRE, Sharepoint, Onedrive). A screenshot of MAGCCINE homepage on Sharepoint database is shown on Figure 1. Backups will be made in a network-attached storage (NAS) disk that will also be synced with the repositories used.
- Project academic partners (U. Porto, CNRS, U. Seville, U. Aveiro, U. Ljubljana) oversee **long-term storage & accessibility**.
- Open-access repositories will ensure data availability **beyond the project duration (minimum 10 years)**.
- **Costs:** Storage, archiving, and data management costs are covered in U. Porto project budget.
- **Responsibilities:** U. Porto oversees data management, with support from all the other members.

FIGURE 1 - MAGCCINE HOMEPAGE ON SHAREPOINT.

6. DATA SECURITY

The MAGCCINE project ensures data security through secure storage, controlled access, and encrypted data transfer where necessary.

- **Secure access control** institutional storage solutions and security protocols will be used for sensitive experimental data, and repositories will follow **trusted data preservation standards**. No personal data is handled, minimising security risks.
- **Compliance with GDPR** where personal data is processed (limited cases).
- Data will be regularly backed up to prevent loss.

7. ETHICS

The **MAGCCINE** project adheres to **strict ethical standards** in data management, ensuring compliance with **GDPR** and ethical research guidelines:

- No **personal or sensitive human** data is processed.
- Ethical considerations relate to **intellectual property and commercial sensitivity**.
- Compliance with **EU ethical guidelines** will be ensured.
- There is no handling of **patient/vaccine recipient data**; the focus is on technology development.

8. HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Publication date	Change
1	06.03.2025	Initial version (new DPM).

